

Energy and electric dipole intensity parameters for the 4*f*-4*f* transitions for the complexation of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with dicyandiamide in different solvents in presence and absence of Ca^{II} to explore the similarities between Ln^{III} and Ca^{II}

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Abstract : Absorption spectral analysis of 4*f*-4*f* transitions for the interaction of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with dicyandiamide (dcda) in presence and absence of Ca^{II} carried out in various organic solvents and their equimolar mixtures. The energy interaction parameters like Slater-Condon (F_k), Racah (E^k), Lande (ξ_{4f}), nephelauxetic effect (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percent co-valency (δ) are calculated to explain the nature of complexation. The changes in the values of oscillator strength (P) and Judd-Ofelt electric dipole intensity parameters (T_λ , $\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) for different 4*f*-4*f* transitions determined experimentally is being used to investigate the mode of binding for the complexes of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with dcda in presence and absence of Ca^{II}.

Keywords : Nephelauxetic effect, hypersensitive, pseudo-hypersensitive, oscillator strength, Judd-Ofelt parameter.

Introduction

Dimensions to lanthanide coordination chemistry in solution become interest with the increased use of lanthanides as PROBES in the exploration of the structural function of biomolecular reactions^{1,3}, specially due to its ability to replace Ca^{II} in a specific manner. Lettvin⁴ first penetrated beyond the mere phenomenology in drawing attention to similarities in the ionic radii of Ca^{II} and Ln^{III} ions. They concluded that Ln^{III} ions could be profitably used to study the interaction of Ca^{II} ion with nerves. Williams⁵ also stated that the similarities between calcium and lanthanide ions are not restricted to their ionic radii but also include important aspects of their coordination chemistry and binding behaviours. Darnall⁶ demonstrated the usefulness of lanthanides as functional replacement for Ca^{II} ions in enzymic reactions. It is as biochemical probes of metal binding sites that Ln^{III} ions have really come into their own and given prominence to the field of lanthanide chemistry. The use of lanthanides as isomorphous replacements for Ca²⁺ is now a standard experimental approach to the study of appropriate biochemical reactions.

Ca^{II} ion which is biologically one of the most important metal ions is chemically one of the least informative.

Because of the way in which the 4*f* electrons are shielded, the absorption spectra do not change dramatically upon complex formation. However, certain absorption peaks, known as hypersensitive peaks respond to the imposition of fields of different strength around the Ln^{III} ion. Upon binding to a ligand many spectral changes are produced like shifting of the peaks, splitting of a peak into several smaller maxima and intensity of the peak. The magnitude of these changes is usually proportional to the strength of the interaction between the Ln^{III} ions and the binding site of ligand (like O > N > S and F > Cl).

The band shape and oscillator strength of these hypersensitive transitions are very sensitive to the environment about the lanthanide ion and obey $|\Delta J| \leq 2$, $|\Delta L| \leq 2$ and $|\Delta S| = 0$ selection rule. In our⁷⁻¹¹ previous work we successfully carried out 4*f*-4*f* spectral analysis of hypersensitive and pseudo hypersensitive transitions of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} during their interactions with many amino acids, polypeptide and other O/N-donor ligands.

The present work reports mainly the quantitative spectral energy interaction parameters and intensity parameters for the complexation of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with dicyandiamide (dcda) in presence and absence of Ca^{II} in different aquated organic solvents and their equimolar

mixtures. It shows the sensitivity of hypersensitive transitions ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{5/2}$ and ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{7/2}$ of Nd^{III} and ligand mediated pseudo hypersensitive transitions ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4F_{3/2}$, ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4F_{5/2}$ and ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4F_{7/2}$ of Nd^{III} and ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$, ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$, ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$ and ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$ transitions of Pr^{III} . The magnitude and variation of Slater-Condon (F_K), Racah (E^k), spin orbit coupling constant (ξ_{4f}), nephelauxetic ratio (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percentage covalency (δ) parameters in support of the intensity parameters like Judd-Ofelt parameters (T_λ , $\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) and oscillator strength (P) are correlated with the binding mode of dicyandiamide.

Experimental

Praseodymium nitrate hexahydrate and neodymium nitrate hexahydrate of 99% purity were purchased from Central Drug House Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi and dicyandiamide (dcda) from Merck. The solvents CH_3CN , CH_3OH , DMF and dioxane of AR grade were obtained from Merck. The saturated solutions of ligand (dcda) and $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}/\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}$ nitrate of $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ have been prepared in different aquated organic solvents (50% v/v). The absorption spectra of the complexes are recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 35 UV-Visible spectrophotometer upgraded with high resolution and expansion of scale in the region 350-910 nm. The temperature for all the observations was maintained at 298 K.

Nephelauxetic ratio¹²⁻¹⁴ has long been regarded as a measure of covalency. The Nephelauxetic effect has been interpreted in terms of Slater-Condon and Racah parameters as well as by the ratio of the complex ion and free ion¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

$$\beta = \frac{F_K^c}{F_K^f} \text{ or } \beta = -\frac{E_c^K}{E_f^K} \quad (1)$$

where F_K ($K = 2, 4, 6$) is the Slater-Condon parameter and E^K is the Racah parameter; c and f stand for complex and free ions respectively. The bonding parameter and percent covalency are calculated as

$$b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1 - \beta}{2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\delta = \left[\frac{1 - \beta}{\beta} \right] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The Slater-Condon parameter also known as direct-integral is a decreasing function of K and is given by

$$F^K = \iint_{0,0}^{\infty, \infty} \frac{r_{<}^K}{r_{>}^{K+1}} R_i^2(r_i) R_j^2(r_j) dr_i dr_j \quad (4)$$

where R is the $4f$ radial wave function, $r_{<}$ and $r_{>}$ are the radii of near and more distant electrons, i and j are the i -th and j -th electrons under consideration. Condon and Shortley¹⁸ redefined F_K integrals in terms of reduced integral F^K related to each other as

$$F_K = \frac{F^K}{D_K} \quad (5)$$

Combining relations (4) and (5), the reduced Slater-Condon integral can be written as

$$F^K = \frac{1}{D_K} \iint_{0,0}^{\infty, \infty} \frac{r_{<}^K}{r_{>}^{K+1}} R_i^2(r_i) R_j^2(r_j) dr_i dr_j \quad (6)$$

where D_K is the denominator and F_K are coefficients of linear combination and represent the angular part of interaction.

In the electronic transition of $4f-4f$, the energy, E_{so} arises from the most important magnetic interactions, while the spin orbit interactions may be written as

$$E_{so} = A_{so} \xi_{4f} \quad (7)$$

where A_{so} is the angular part of spin orbit interaction and ξ_{4f} is the radial integral and is known as Lande's parameter. By first order approximation, the energy E_j of the j -th level is given by Wong¹⁹ as

$$E_j(F_K, \xi_{4f}) = E_{0j}(F_K^0, \xi_{4f}^0) + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial F_K} \Delta F_K + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial \xi_{4f}} \Delta \xi_{4f} \quad (8)$$

where E_{0j} is the zero order of the j^{th} level. The values of F_K and ξ_{4f} are given by

$$F_K = F_K^0 + \Delta F_K \quad (9)$$

$$\xi_{4f} = \xi_{4f}^0 + \Delta \xi_{4f}$$

The difference between the observed E_j value and the zero order value, ΔE_j is evaluated by

$$\Delta E_j = \sum_{K=2,4,6} \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial F_K} \Delta F_K + \frac{\partial E_j}{\partial \xi_{4f}} \Delta \xi_{4f} \quad (10)$$

By using the zero order energy and partial derivatives of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} ion given by Wong²⁰, the above equation

can be solved by least square technique and the values of ΔF_k and $\Delta \xi_{4f}$ can be found out. From these values, the values of F_2 , F_4 , F_6 and ξ_{4f} are found out by using relation (9).

The calculation of the band intensities is based upon the theoretical treatment derived by Judd²¹ and Ofelt²². They considered the transitions are essentially electric dipole in character and the oscillator strength corresponding to the induced electric dipole transition $\psi_j \rightarrow \psi_{j'}$ is given by

$$P_{\text{cald.}} = \sum_{\lambda=2,4,6} T_\lambda \bar{\nu} \left\langle f^n \psi_j \left\| U^{(\lambda)} \right\| f^n \psi_{j'} \right\rangle^2 \quad (11)$$

where $U^{(\lambda)}$ is the matrix element of unit tensor operator connecting initial $\langle f^n \psi_j |$ and final $| f^n \psi_{j'} \rangle$ through three phenomenological parameters T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) called Judd-Ofelt parameters. These parameters are related to the radial parts of 4*f*^N wave functions, the wave functions of perturbing configurations of which the nearest is 4*f*^{N-1} 5*d*. The matrix elements used for intensity analysis of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes given by Carnall²³.

The experimental value of oscillator strength (P_{obsd}) of absorption bands were calculated by Gaussian curve analysis using the following relationship

$$P_{\text{obsd}} = 4.6 \times 10^{-9} \times \epsilon_{\text{max}} \times \Delta \bar{\nu}_{1/2} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) is the energy of the transition and ϵ_{max} is the molar extinction coefficient. From these values, the values of T_2 , T_4 and T_6 are calculated by partial and multiple regression method using the Judd-Ofelt expression.

$$\frac{P_{\text{obsd.}}}{\bar{\nu}} = \left[(U^2) \right]^2 T_2 + \left[(U^4) \right]^2 T_4 + \left[(U^6) \right]^2 T_6 \quad (13)$$

Results and discussion

The transitions involving 4*f*-4*f* transitions are very sensitive towards immediate coordination environment around lanthanide ion. Judd²⁴ marked the hypersensitivity due to the changes in symmetry of the environment of a lanthanide ion. Pr^{III} ions observed four transitions (³H₄ → ³P₂, ³P₁, ³P₀, ¹D₂) originating from symmetry forbidden ground level in the 400–600 nm spectral region. In Nd^{III}, the transition, ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{5/2} obeys selection rule which is very sensitive to the environment and usually more intense when a lanthanide ion gets com-

plexed than it is in the corresponding aquo ion. Hence, the above transition is called hypersensitive transition. And the transitions ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴I_{3/2}, ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴F_{5/2}, ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴F_{7/2} and ⁴I_{9/2} → ⁴G_{7/2} do not obey the selection rules for hypersensitive transition but have been found to exhibit substantial sensitivity in the complexes. Such transitions are called ligand-mediated pseudo hypersensitive transition. The comparative absorption spectra of Pr^{III}; Pr^{III} : dcda (1 : 1), Pr^{III} : dcda : Ca (1 : 1 : 1) in DMF is shown in Figs. 1(a) and 2(a) gives that of Nd^{III}; Nd^{III} : dcda (1 : 1) and Nd^{III} : dcda : Ca^{II} (1 : 1 : 1) in DMF. The addition of ligand to the metal ion results in the red shift in all the energy bands but the changes in the intensity data are seen from the intensification of the 4*f*-4*f* transition bands when the ligand is added. The intensification of bands especially ³H₄ → ³P₂ can be correlated with lowering of coordination number and shortening of the metal-ligand bond distance. Table 1 gives the values of energy interaction parameters like Slater-Condon (F_k), Racah (E^k), spin orbit coupling constant (ξ_{4f}), nephelauxetic ratio (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percentage covalency (δ) parameters in aqueous and different aquated organic solvents for free Pr^{III} ion; Pr^{III} : dcda and Pr^{III} : dcda : Ca^{II}. Table 2 gives all the parameters for Nd^{III} ion; Nd^{III} : dcda and Nd^{III} : dcda : Ca^{II}. Table 3 shows the variation of solvent nature which has significant effect on the intensity parameters like oscillator strength (P) of different 4*f*-4*f* bands leading to substantial variation in the magnitudes of Judd-Ofelt electric dipole intensity parameters (T_λ , $\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) of Pr^{III} complexes. And Table 4 gives the oscillator strength of Nd^{III} complexes and magnitudes of Judd-Ofelt parameters of Nd^{III} complexes are given in Table 2.

From Tables 1 and 2 one can observe that in all the systems there is decrease in Slater-Condon (F_k), Racah (E^k) and spin-orbit interaction (ξ_{4f}) which indicates lowering of both coulombic (F_k) and spin-orbit interaction (ξ_{4f}) parameters thus leading to the expansion of the central metal ion orbital when ligand is added to Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} ion. And also one can observe that the decrease values in energy is more in case of complexes when DMF is used as the organic solvent or DMF as one of the organic solvents in their equimolar mixtures whereas CH₃OH is the least. The values of nephelauxetic ratio in all the systems ranges from 0.9443 to 0.9470 for Pr^{III} ion

Fig. 1(a). Comparative absorption spectra of complexes (a) Pr^{III} , (b) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda}$ (1 : 1) and (c) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda} : \text{Ca}$ (1 : 1 : 1), where dcda = dicyandiamide in DMF.

Fig. 1(b). Comparative absorption spectra of complexes of $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda}$ complexes in presence of Ca^{II} in (a) DMF, (b) CH_3CN , (c) dioxane and (d) CH_3OH .

while that of Nd^{III} ion ranges from 0.0413 to 0.0927 which is less than unity and the values of bonding parameter are found to be positive which correlates covalent bonding. The corresponding oscillator strength of complexes of Pr^{III} with dicyandiamide (dcda) in presence and absence of Ca^{2+} in the solvents CH_3OH , CH_3CN , diox-

ane and DMF are presented in Table 3. The marked intensification of the band is found when DMF is used as the organic solvent or one of the organic solvents in their equimolar mixtures. We have noted distinctly different band shapes for the transitions ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2, {}^3P_1, {}^3P_0$ and 1D_2 in CH_3OH , CH_3CN , dioxane and DMF medium rela-

Fig. 2(a). Comparative absorption spectra of complexes (a) Nd^{III} , (b) $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda} (1 : 1)$ and (c) $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda} : \text{Ca} (1 : 1 : 1)$ in DMF solvent, where dcda = dicyandiamide.

Fig. 2(b). Comparative absorption spectra of $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda}$ in (a) DMF (b) dioxane (c) CH_3CN - - - - - and (d) CH_3OH ———.

tive to the complex $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{dicyandiamide} (\text{dcda})$. The sensitivities of the intensification of bands of the four transitions of $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{dcda}$ complexes are shown in Fig. 1(b), where the order of sensitivities are $\text{DMF} > \text{CH}_3\text{CN} > \text{dioxane} > \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. DMF generally binds through

oxygen and not nitrogen when it coordinates to hard acids like the lanthanide ions whereas CH_3CN binds through nitrogen. The higher intensification in DMF medium also reveals the stronger bonding capacity of oxygen than nitrogen. Methanol is a very weak donor. And the corre-

Table 1. Computed values of energy interaction Slater-Condon F_k (cm^{-1}) and Lande spin orbit coupling ξ_{4f} (cm^{-1}), Racah E^k (cm^{-1}), Nephelauxetic ratio (β) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and covalency parameters (δ) of Pr^{III} , $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$ (1 : 1) and $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1), where L = dicyandiamide in aqueous and different aquated organic solvents (50 : 50) are given below

System	F_2	F_4	F_6	ξ_{4f}	E^1	E^2	E^3	β	$b^{1/2}$	δ
(1) H_2O										
Pr^{III}	309.31	42.70	4.67	722.54	3512.13	23.76	614.93	0.9470	0.1627	5.5912
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.30	42.69	4.67	722.52	3512.04	23.76	614.91	0.9470	0.1628	5.5941
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.29	42.69	4.67	722.49	3511.95	23.76	614.90	0.9470	0.1628	5.5971
(2) CH_3OH										
Pr^{III}	309.32	42.70	4.67	722.16	3512.24	23.76	614.95	0.9468	0.1631	5.6180
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.31	42.70	4.67	722.14	3512.15	23.76	614.93	0.9468	0.1631	5.6210
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.30	42.69	4.67	722.16	3512.03	23.76	614.91	0.9468	0.1631	5.6216
(3) CH_3CN										
Pr^{III}	309.26	42.69	4.66	722.63	3511.52	23.76	614.82	0.9470	0.1627	5.5930
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.25	42.69	4.66	722.62	3511.44	23.76	614.81	0.9470	0.1628	5.5951
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.24	42.69	4.66	722.59	3511.35	23.76	614.79	0.9470	0.1628	5.5982
(4) DMF										
Pr^{III}	308.94	42.64	4.66	719.37	3507.89	23.73	614.19	0.9443	0.1668	5.8948
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	308.93	42.64	4.66	719.33	3507.80	23.73	614.17	0.9443	0.1669	5.8988
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	308.92	42.64	4.66	719.31	3507.71	23.73	614.15	0.9443	0.1669	5.9018
(5) Dioxane										
Pr^{III}	309.29	42.69	4.67	722.25	3511.88	23.76	614.89	0.9468	0.1631	5.6168
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.27	42.69	4.67	722.23	3511.73	23.76	614.86	0.9468	0.1631	5.6201
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.26	42.69	4.67	722.20	3511.63	23.76	614.84	0.9468	0.1632	5.6241
(6) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$										
Pr^{III}	309.32	42.70	4.67	722.42	3512.22	23.76	614.94	0.9470	0.1628	5.5990
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.31	42.70	4.67	722.42	3512.08	23.76	614.92	0.9470	0.1628	5.6005
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.29	42.69	4.67	722.39	3511.98	23.76	614.90	0.9469	0.1629	5.6045
(7) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{DMF}$										
Pr^{III}	309.09	42.66	4.66	720.61	3509.61	23.75	614.49	0.9454	0.1652	5.7750
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.08	42.66	4.66	720.55	3509.50	23.74	614.47	0.9454	0.1653	5.7807
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.06	42.66	4.66	720.44	3509.33	23.74	614.44	0.9452	0.1655	5.7922
(8) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{dioxane}$										
Pr^{III}	309.32	42.70	4.67	722.44	3512.20	23.76	614.94	0.9470	0.1628	5.5976
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.29	42.69	4.67	722.33	3511.97	23.76	614.90	0.9469	0.1630	5.6095
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.26	42.69	4.66	721.91	3511.54	23.76	614.83	0.9465	0.1635	5.6475
(9) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{DMF}$										
Pr^{III}	309.12	42.67	4.66	721.02	3510.00	23.75	614.56	0.9457	0.1647	5.7376
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.11	42.67	4.66	720.97	3509.89	23.75	614.54	0.9457	0.1648	5.7433
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.11	42.67	4.66	720.95	3509.80	23.75	614.52	0.9457	0.1648	5.7462
(10) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{dioxane}$										
Pr^{III}	309.31	42.70	4.67	722.52	3512.14	23.76	614.93	0.9470	0.1627	5.5922
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.30	42.69	4.67	722.51	3511.99	23.76	614.91	0.9470	0.1628	5.5954
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.29	42.69	4.67	722.49	3511.91	23.76	614.89	0.9470	0.1628	5.5983
(11) DMF : dioxane										
Pr^{III}	309.12	42.67	4.66	721.08	3509.91	23.75	614.54	0.9458	0.1647	5.7343
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	309.11	42.67	4.66	721.04	3509.81	23.75	614.52	0.9457	0.1647	5.7390
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	309.09	42.67	4.66	720.97	3509.68	23.75	614.50	0.9457	0.1648	5.7464

Table 2. Computed values of energy interaction Slater-Condon F_k (cm^{-1}) and Lande spin orbit coupling ξ_{4f} (cm^{-1}), Nephelauxtic ratio (β) and bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$), covalency parameters (δ) and Judd-Ofelt parameters ($T_\lambda \times 10^{-10}$) of Nd^{III} , $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$ (1 : 1) and $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1), where L = dicyandiamide in aqueous and different aquated organic solvents (50 : 50) are given below

System	F_2	F_4	F_6	ξ_{4f}	β	$b^{1/2}$	δ	T_2	T_4	T_6
(1) H_2O										
Nd^{III}	332.06	48.61	5.10	897.74	0.0633	0.9919	0.8085	1.5366	-0.1286	5.7423
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	332.06	48.61	5.10	897.87	0.0630	0.9920	0.8011	1.5084	-0.0512	5.7592
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	332.05	48.61	5.10	898.01	0.0626	0.9921	0.7922	1.5586	-0.0652	5.7724
(2) CH_3OH										
Nd^{III}	331.98	48.60	5.10	899.47	0.0589	0.9930	0.7009	2.2764	-1.1877	4.4283
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.97	48.60	5.10	899.71	0.0583	0.9931	0.6851	2.3256	-1.1087	4.5087
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.96	48.60	5.10	899.97	0.0577	0.9933	0.6703	2.2845	-0.9949	4.5090
(3) CH_3CN										
Nd^{III}	331.94	48.62	5.10	899.77	0.0581	0.9932	0.6803	1.5879	-0.0073	5.6648
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.93	48.61	5.10	899.97	0.0577	0.9933	0.6699	1.6502	-0.0087	5.8298
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.91	48.61	5.10	900.28	0.0569	0.9935	0.6524	1.7336	0.0159	5.9217
(4) DMF										
Nd^{III}	329.38	50.05	5.28	926.15	0.0923	1.0170	1.6736	3.6233	-0.1873	6.4568
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	329.37	51.05	5.28	926.33	0.0925	1.0171	1.6828	3.6546	-0.1926	6.5704
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	321.36	50.05	5.28	926.46	0.0927	1.0172	1.6906	3.7522	-0.1826	6.6881
(5) Dioxane										
Nd^{III}	331.94	48.59	5.10	900.29	0.0572	0.9935	0.6579	2.4681	-1.1018	4.8398
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.92	48.59	5.10	900.60	0.0563	0.9937	0.6382	2.4164	-0.9157	4.9033
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.90	48.59	5.10	900.95	0.0554	0.9939	0.6179	2.4112	-0.7735	4.9403
(6) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$										
Nd^{III}	332.03	48.61	5.10	898.59	0.0610	0.9925	0.7515	1.7805	-0.1753	5.7157
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	332.02	48.61	5.10	898.76	0.0606	0.9926	0.7406	1.7699	-0.1457	5.8244
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	332.01	48.61	5.10	898.95	0.0602	0.9927	0.7305	1.8517	-0.1436	5.9549
(7) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{DMF}$										
Nd^{III}	331.53	48.63	5.17	914.68	0.0413	1.0034	0.3407	3.0805	-0.0653	6.1353
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.52	48.63	5.17	914.87	0.0421	1.0035	0.3526	3.1306	-0.0373	6.4205
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.52	48.63	5.17	914.99	0.0425	1.0036	0.3598	3.2677	-0.1694	6.7717
(8) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{Dioxane}$										
Nd^{III}	331.95	48.60	5.10	900.22	0.0572	0.9934	0.6592	1.9707	-0.1473	5.7897
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.93	48.59	5.10	900.45	0.0566	0.9935	0.6463	1.9472	-0.0405	5.8732
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.90	48.59	5.10	900.89	0.0557	0.9937	0.6251	1.9271	0.1002	5.9873
(9) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{DMF}$										
Nd^{III}	331.54	48.63	5.17	914.68	0.0413	1.0034	0.3407	3.0034	-0.1031	6.1743
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.53	48.63	5.17	914.87	0.0420	1.0035	0.3526	3.0817	-0.1260	6.3795
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.52	48.63	5.17	914.99	0.0424	1.0036	0.3598	3.0571	0.0091	6.4764
(10) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{dioxane}$										
Nd^{III}	332.03	48.61	5.10	898.91	0.0603	0.9927	0.7324	2.0678	-0.6294	5.4768
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	332.01	48.61	5.10	899.15	0.0598	0.9929	0.7191	2.0253	-0.5452	5.6919
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.99	48.60	5.10	899.40	0.0592	0.9930	0.7052	2.0593	-0.5080	5.8941
(11) DMF : dioxane										
Nd^{III}	331.50	48.60	5.17	915.58	0.0436	1.0038	0.3791	2.8925	-0.1931	5.7025
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	331.49	48.61	5.17	915.75	0.0442	1.0039	0.3906	2.8915	-0.0838	5.7179
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	331.48	48.60	5.17	915.91	0.0448	1.0040	0.4010	2.9390	-0.1222	5.8562

Table 3. Computed and observed values of oscillator strengths ($P \times 10^6$) and Judd-Ofelt parameters ($T \times 10^{-10}$) for Pr^{III} , $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$ (1 : 1) and $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1), where L = dicyandiamide in aqueous and different aquated organic solvents (50 : 50) are given below

System	${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$		${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$		T_2	T_4	T_6
	P_{obsd}	P_{cald}	P_{obsd}	P_{cald}	P_{obsd}	P_{cald}	P_{obsd}	P_{cald}			
(1) H_2O											
Pr^{III}	3.5853	3.5853	1.0109	0.7774	0.5356	0.7655	0.9168	0.9168	-29.82	2.1344	11.178
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.6204	3.6204	1.0502	0.8063	0.5538	0.7940	0.8310	0.8310	-51.65	2.2138	11.272
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.6094	3.6094	1.0264	0.7962	0.5574	0.7841	0.9860	0.9860	-15.78	2.1863	11.244
(2) CH_3OH											
Pr^{III}	3.6120	3.6120	1.0259	0.7823	0.5304	0.7703	0.9469	0.9469	-24.67	2.1476	11.262
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.6355	3.6355	1.0425	0.7958	0.5407	0.7836	0.9405	0.9405	-27.70	2.1848	11.329
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.7475	3.7475	0.9751	0.7566	0.5299	0.7450	0.9393	0.9393	-35.19	2.0773	11.726
(3) CH_3CN											
Pr^{III}	3.5375	3.5375	1.0565	0.8034	0.5419	0.7911	0.7777	0.7777	-58.30	2.2061	11.004
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.6291	3.6291	1.0759	0.8122	0.5400	0.7997	1.0052	1.0052	-12.79	2.2302	11.298
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.5510	3.5510	1.0792	0.8072	0.5269	0.7947	0.6805	0.6805	-81.23	2.2165	11.046
(4) DMF											
Pr^{III}	4.2531	4.2531	1.2454	0.9921	0.7278	0.9774	0.8998	0.8998	-77.74	2.7265	13.233
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	4.3432	4.3432	1.2713	1.0117	0.7409	0.9967	0.9845	0.9845	-64.45	2.7804	13.515
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	4.3773	4.3773	1.2576	1.0058	0.7429	0.9909	0.8554	0.8554	-96.05	2.7645	13.631
(5) Dioxane											
Pr^{III}	3.4254	3.4254	1.0701	0.8015	0.5248	0.7893	0.9481	0.9481	-12.22	2.2007	10.637
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.5338	3.5338	1.0618	0.8129	0.5553	0.8004	0.9058	0.9058	-28.95	2.2319	10.984
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.5390	3.5390	1.0590	0.8060	0.5445	0.7937	0.9095	0.9095	-28.44	2.2131	11.006
(6) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$											
Pr^{III}	3.2185	3.2185	1.4985	1.0401	0.5725	1.0237	0.7682	0.7682	-40.21	2.8543	9.7832
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.2832	3.2832	1.2278	0.9122	0.5873	0.8979	0.7740	0.7740	-42.71	2.5036	10.089
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.2872	3.2872	1.2578	0.9257	0.5844	0.9113	0.7802	0.7802	-41.62	2.5409	10.093
(7) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{DMF}$											
Pr^{III}	4.2400	4.2400	1.1725	0.9503	1.7172	0.9360	1.2185	1.2185	-4.540	2.6106	13.212
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	4.2943	4.2943	1.1615	0.9964	0.8187	0.9814	1.2737	1.2737	4.296	2.7371	13.357
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	4.2350	4.2350	1.1786	0.9459	0.7025	0.9317	1.1508	1.1508	-19.51	2.5986	13.200
(8) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{dioxane}$											
Pr^{III}	3.0303	3.0303	1.0830	0.7920	0.4933	0.7798	0.5355	0.5355	-79.86	2.1743	9.3489
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.1060	3.1060	1.1320	0.8264	0.5127	0.8137	0.9928	0.9928	18.73	2.2687	9.5722
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.1325	3.1325	1.1347	0.8298	0.5168	0.8170	0.7402	0.7402	-40.15	2.2782	9.6567
(9) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{DMF}$											
Pr^{III}	4.0052	4.0052	1.1664	0.9242	0.6717	0.9102	1.0198	1.0198	-34.22	2.5387	12.457
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	4.2172	4.2172	1.2323	0.9624	0.682	0.9479	1.1827	1.1827	-11.26	2.6436	13.125
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	4.1837	4.1837	1.2371	0.9622	0.6769	0.9477	1.1691	1.1691	-12.14	2.6432	13.016
(10) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{dioxane}$											
Pr^{III}	3.2559	3.2559	1.2210	0.8962	0.5626	0.8823	1.1693	1.1693	48.633	2.4602	10.012
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	3.3170	3.3107	1.2414	0.9138	0.5771	0.8996	0.7672	0.7672	-46.53	2.5084	10.199
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	3.3328	3.3328	1.2298	0.9016	0.5644	0.8875	0.7034	0.7034	-61.98	2.4749	10.260
(11) DMF : dioxane											
Pr^{III}	3.9525	3.9525	0.8775	0.7270	0.5677	0.716	0.7677	0.7677	-87.38	1.9969	12.430
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$	4.3825	4.3865	0.9735	0.8002	0.6175	0.7881	1.2635	1.2635	-3.522	2.1983	13.800
$\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	4.3299	4.3299	0.9534	0.7808	0.5991	0.769	1.0684	1.0684	-44.02	2.1451	13.629

sponding oscillator strength of Nd^{III} complexes with dcda in presence and absence of Ca^{2+} in the solvents CH_3OH , CH_3CN , dioxane and DMF and their equimolar mixtures are presented in Table 4. The sensitivities of the intensification of bands of the transitions of Nd^{III} : dcda com-

plexes in the solvents CH_3OH , CH_3CN , dioxane and DMF are shown in Fig. 2(b), where the order of sensitivities are $\text{DMF} > \text{dioxane} > \text{CH}_3\text{CN} > \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. The sensitivities of $4f-4f$ transitions are usually characterized by large values of $U^{(2)}$ matrix elements and contributed signifi-

Table 4. Computed and observed values of oscillator strengths ($P \times 10^6$) for Nd^{III} , $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L}$ (1 : 1) and $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$ (1 : 1 : 1), where L = dicyandiamide in aqueous and different aquted organic solvents (50 : 50) are given below

System	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{7/2}$		$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{9/2}$		$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$		$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}$		$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	
	P_{obsd}	P_{cald}								
(1) H_2O										
Nd^{III}	0.8246	0.7258	2.6545	2.66	3.4243	3.2918	2.6825	2.8366	0.4193	0.329
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.8545	0.7479	2.6661	2.6721	3.4206	3.3058	2.7335	2.868	0.4224	0.3506
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	0.8889	0.7504	2.7336	2.7412	3.4341	3.3126	2.7272	2.8705	0.4157	0.3477
(2) CH_3OH										
Nd^{III}	0.7726	0.3475	2.9548	2.9784	3.1175	2.4781	1.1229	1.8647	0.4164	-0.0356
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.8224	0.3849	3.0917	3.116	3.1589	2.5288	1.1965	1.9285	0.4303	-0.0096
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	0.86	0.4148	3.108	0.3763	3.1817	2.5354	1.2117	1.9623	0.4729	0.0207
(3) CH_3CN										
Nd^{III}	0.9205	0.7594	2.812	2.8209	3.3661	3.2537	2.6992	2.8332	0.4091	0.3562
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.9529	0.7829	2.9178	2.9272	3.4577	3.3484	2.7845	2.9154	0.4135	0.3662
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	1.0057	0.8087	3.0694	3.0804	3.5106	3.4026	2.8383	2.9687	0.4164	0.3785
(4) DMF										
Nd^{III}	1.2775	1.0024	5.8611	5.8763	3.7048	3.664	3.0986	3.156	0.3117	0.358
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	1.3337	1.016	5.9102	5.9279	3.8033	3.7282	3.1125	3.2108	0.335	0.3638
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	1.3783	1.0416	6.0746	6.0933	3.8904	3.7957	3.151	3.2723	0.3573	0.3739
(5) Dioxane										
Nd^{III}	0.9439	0.4367	3.3354	3.3635	3.3445	2.7194	1.3672	2.0963	0.4269	0.0132
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.9764	0.4939	3.3922	3.419	3.3691	2.7663	1.4804	2.1832	0.4677	0.0667
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	0.9913	0.5399	3.4891	3.5142	3.3714	2.7956	1.5729	2.2439	0.4928	0.1068
(6) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{CH}_3\text{CN}$										
Nd^{III}	0.828	0.7347	3.0003	3.0054	3.3413	3.2741	2.7294	2.8094	0.3473	0.3148
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.86	0.7539	3.0106	3.0166	3.4216	3.3381	2.7736	2.8725	0.3728	0.3295
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	0.8878	0.7768	3.1475	3.1537	3.5128	3.4132	2.8211	2.9385	0.3949	0.3383
(7) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{DMF}$										
Nd^{III}	1.1618	0.9485	5.0933	5.105	3.6341	3.5205	2.9127	3.0499	0.4082	0.3702
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	1.2923	0.9921	5.2032	5.2198	3.8233	3.6858	3.0326	3.2007	0.4285	0.3957
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	1.3624	1.0036	5.3405	5.3604	4.0603	3.8799	3.118	3.3371	0.4368	0.3828
(8) $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} : \text{dioxane}$										
Nd^{III}	0.8627	0.7708	3.3203	3.3253	3.4195	-3.3183	2.7361	2.8545	0.3908	0.3269
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	0.9232	0.8092	3.3634	3.3697	3.4615	3.3723	2.8222	2.928	0.4067	0.3605
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	0.9895	0.8613	3.4384	3.4455	3.497	3.4457	2.9633	3.0267	0.4123	0.4051
(9) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{DMF}$										
Nd^{III}	1.0986	0.9332	4.954	4.963	3.6446	3.5406	2.9337	3.0583	0.4065	0.3627
$\text{Nd} : \text{L}$	1.1499	0.9561	5.0699	5.0806	3.7702	3.657	3.018	3.1541	0.4129	0.3696
$\text{Nd}^{\text{III}} : \text{L} : \text{Ca}^{\text{II}}$	1.215	1.0042	5.1322	5.1438	3.7934	3.7202	3.1511	3.2426	0.4134	0.4116

(10) CH ₃ CN : dioxane										
Nd ^{III}	0.8827	0.6034	3.0995	3.1151	3.4098	3.1116	2.2059	2.5552	0.3649	0.179
Nd : L	0.8959	0.6468	3.1081	3.1219	3.5139	3.2398	2.3669	2.6878	0.3882	0.215
Nd ^{III} : L : Ca ^{II}	0.9073	0.6827	3.2012	3.2138	3.6256	3.358	2.4875	2.8	0.4125	0.2377
(11) DMF : dioxane										
Nd ^{III}	1.0226	0.8448	4.6881	4.698	3.2945	3.2651	2.7549	2.7954	0.2809	0.309
Nd : L	1.1150	0.8792	4.7613	4.7745	3.3201	3.28	2.7805	2.8355	0.3028	0.3389
Nd ^{III} : L : Ca ^{II}	1.1612	0.8871	4.814	4.8293	3.421	3.3572	2.8097	2.8932	0.3112	0.3375

cant variation of Judd-Ofelt electric dipole T_2 -parameter.

For Pr^{III} complexes, the transition $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3F_2$ (hyper-sensitive) occurring around 5200 cm^{-1} has not been observed in most of the spectral studies especially in solution as it is beyond the range of UV-region.

The experimental oscillator strength of different transitions and the values of Judd-Ofelt (T_λ) intensity parameters for Pr^{III} complexes are given in Tables 3 and 4 gives that of Nd^{III} complexes. From Tables 3 and 4, it has been observed that the increased in the values of oscillator strength as well as Judd-Ofelt (T_λ) ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) intensity parameters when the ligand (dcda) is added to the Pr^{III}/Nd^{III} ion and further increase when Ca²⁺ ions are added as shown in Figs. 1(a) and 2(a). The increased in the values of oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt intensity T_λ ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) parameters indicates complexation where T_2 is negative and is meaningless. Hence, it is favoured by T_4 and T_6 followed by T_2 .

Conclusion :

From the investigations, it is revealed that the $4f-4f$ transitions of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} have been used to indicate the nature of binding between metal ion and the ligand. The decrease in the values of inter electronic repulsion parameters such as Slater-Condon (F_k), Racah (E^k), Lande (ξ_{4f}), nephelauxetic effect (β), bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$) and percent covalency (δ) and increased values of oscillator strength (P) and Judd-Ofelt electric dipole intensity parameters (T_λ) ($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) indicate expansion of central metal ion when ligand is added and further on addition of Ca²⁺ ion. This leads to lowering of coordination number and shortening of the metal-ligand bond distance. From the studies of complexation of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with dicyandiamide (dcda) by using solvents (DMF, CH₃CN, dioxane, CH₃OH), it is also observed that DMF is the

most intensified solvent or one of the solvents in their equimolar mixtures whereas CH₃OH is the least. It has been found that the order of sensitivities of the transitions of complexes relative to Pr^{III} : dcda is DMF > CH₃CN > dioxane > CH₃OH and that of Nd^{III} : dcda is DMF > dioxane > CH₃CN > CH₃OH.

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